

DEVELOPMENT OF LIBRARIES IN CULTURAL CENTERS

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Abstract: This article talks about the activity of libraries, further strengthening of promotion of readers in libraries and formation of information culture.

Key words: information, library, education, need, spirituality

It is no secret that the book has a special place in people's lives, because the book is considered a wonderful tool that encourages people to do good and turns them back to evil by fundamentally reforming their thoughts about evil. Today, the great attention paid to reading and reading books in our country encourages the people of this profession to work more actively. Because an ordinary schoolboy who has not yet boarded the ship of thinking, who has not yet swum in the sea of ideas, enters the magic-mysterious room in a corner of the educational institution, when he is unexpectedly greeted by a kind person, who, based on his age and interest, offers him a few books. If he tells such interesting stories about those books, his impressions, any reader will forget the whole world and become engrossed in reading, and then fall in love with that bright place every day. Even in the psychology of the youth of the world, it is observed that the attitude towards family, i.e. relations between parents and children, the culture of reading books, the attitude towards national and religious values is cooling, and the tendencies of alienation are increasing. Mamlakatimizda mana shunday holatlarning oldini olish, o‘quvchi-yoshlarni turli yot g‘oyalar, tahdidlardan himoya qilish, ularning tarbiyasini to‘g‘ri amalga oshirish borasida qator vazifalar

belgilanib, chora-tadbirlari ishlab chiqilmoqda. Buning samarasi o'laroq qolgan davlatlarga ham o'rnak bo'la oladigan dasturlar ishlab chiqilgan.

For example, the Honorable President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in his speech at the extended meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers dedicated to "The main results of the socio-economic development of our country in 2016 and the most important priorities of the economic program for 2017" , science, defined a number of tasks related to the implementation of the state's youth policy. Among these, we can mention the following opinions on the formation of the interest of students and young people in reading artistic, scientific and historical literature: It is our task to take our work to a new level aimed at further increasing their love and spiritual immunity." In fact, by forming a culture of reading in students and young people, increasing their interest in reading, studying and analyzing scientific and historical works, ideological immunity to various foreign ideas is created in them. Science, society's achievements and progress are made with books, we hear a lot of opinions and ideas that books are the best teacher in youth, and there is no better friend in old age. 2. in order to support their development, they will promote literature. They should consider satisfying their curiosity as one of their main tasks. For this purpose, they determine the ways of recommending the most necessary literature that contributes to the foundation of proficiency for each reader, taking into account their own characteristics. Librarians must have a good idea of their tasks and strictly follow the tasks of providing information-library services in their daily activities.

is the formation of a developed personality. Based on this goal, important tasks such as the promotion of literature on the upbringing of a mature generation, the development of literature on this topic, a series of events that can be held, determine the main aspects of the work of information-resource and information-library centers. Mental maturity represents high scientific knowledge, culture and sophistication, while physical maturity represents the reader's overall physical health. The combination of mental and physical maturity in the reader is a sign of maturity. The development of the reader in all aspects affects his spiritual development as well. It makes him the

owner of modern knowledge, an enlightened, cultured person. There is no limit to the all-round development of a person, and the student for him keeps multiplying like new-born dreams. All-round perfection of the person does not put the idea that the reader must fully master all fields of science. It is necessary that the consumer's profession and specialty serve as the main factor in the unique aspiration. The library cooperates and influences the all-round development of the person, but it should provide an opportunity to freely choose and evaluate literature, protecting the rights of the reader without imposing pressure on the reader. The main goal of providing services to consumers is the comprehensive development of the individual, which serves as the methodological basis for organizing all the information and library services of the library and public educational institutions. The library, ICMs closely support their users in forming new interests, deepening and developing their interests. They have a certain influence on the expansion of the scope of reading consumers.

The results of these works are reflected in the choice of books by consumers, the development of their thinking, and the formation of their interest. There is also a tradition of group discussion about the book read in the experience of libraries. In this case, it is better to have a conversation after some time about the work that excited the children. Because during this period, the child has different opinions about the book he has read, and even the reader has mutually exclusive views. After that, it is better for the librarian to first listen to the opinion of the readers about this work, and at the end of the conversation, he should give his opinion. As a result, students develop the ability to understand and think about the book. At the same time, the librarian, taking into account the reading level of each student, teaches them the ways to learn the most necessary and important things from the book, leads them to read more complex books than simple books, depending on their ability and ability. A book is full of events, and with these events, it influences a person's thoughts and eventually becomes his best friend.

References:

1. 1.www.ziyo.uz online kutubxonasi
2. 2.Muxtorov A. Shaxs tarbiyasida milliy g‘oya, ehtiyoj va man'aatlar uyg'unligi.-Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2003
3. 3.O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2010 yil 29 dekabrdagi “2011-2015 yillarda madaniyat va istirohat bog‘larining moddiy-texnika bazasini mustahkamlash va ularni tijtlig faoliyatini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari dasturmi tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida”gi 322-sonli qarori.